

1 EGFR and MET growth factor signaling during TE commitment.

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of EGFR
9 and MET growth factor signaling pathways as critical for lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of
10 the human embryo.

11 We previously demonstrated a concomitant mobilization of EGFR, MET and the Hippo signaling pathway
12 as a basic component function of transformation in mammals. Accordingly, FAT3, a Hippo-pathway
13 cadherin was a component gene in the TE differentiation program.

14 Citations

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1. Chia, C.M., Winston, R.M. and Handyside, A.H., 1995. EGF, TGF- α and EGFR expression in
human preimplantation embryos. *Development*, 121(2), pp.299-307.